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Do middle school students consider 'conducting tests' to be important to engineering design?

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ABSTRACT

Testing and experimentation are vital parts of the innovation process and also a critical practice of engineers. In this study, we examine secondary school students' understanding of this critical practice. We focus our analysis on K-12 education, where teaching engineering practices and core ideas are gaining momentum as part of the STEM education movement. We collected data from 746 middle school students using the Conceptions of Design Test (CDT), eliciting student's views of importance of conducting tests in design. CDT asks students to select five design practices from a list 20 and asks students to explain why they believe the practices they have selected are critical to informed design. We performed McNemar tests to quantitatively analyze students' changing conceptions of design before and after completing a design project. We also used the thematic analysis approach to qualitatively analyze variations in students' perceptions of 'conducting tests.' We found that after a design activity, "conducting tests" became a statistically more important practice to students. Students' explanations reflected two types of conceptualization of conducting tests: diagnose-fix iterative cycle and transformative iterative cycle.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there have been many efforts by researchers and educators to integrate engineering design into K-12 education. As part of these efforts, students engage in engineering design while performing design practices such as problem scoping, sketching, conducting tests, and communicating. While there are studies on expert designer' and undergraduate students' understanding of these practices [1–4], very few studies have been conducted at the K-12 level [5–7].

Engineering in K-12 classrooms is often taught by science teachers, who are familiar with scientific inquiry but not as familiar with the design inquiry, Both engineering design and scientific inquiry involve common reasoning processes (e.g., reasoning from evidence), cognitive activities (e.g., asking questions, evaluating, and inquiry practices (e.g., conducting experiments, communicating) [8]. Yet, these processes, activities, and practices have different purposes reflecting the epistemological differences between the two disciplines. The scientist asks questions to understand natural phenomena often decontextualized to form generalizations while the engineer asks questions to understand the constraints of a problem that is highly contextualized [8,9].

In this study, we focus on "conducting tests and experiments", a practice important in both science and engineering. In addition, experimentation is also a vital practice in innovation, as many innovators experiment with ideas, test design performances, and compare alternatives before pursuing ideas further [10]. Hence, we investigated students' conceptualization and prioritization of conducting tests in design as we answer the following research questions:

1. Do students' *prioritization* of "conducting tests" as a design practice change after completing an engineering design project? and

2. How do students *conceptualize* “conducting tests”?

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The practice of conducting tests and experiments is common to both science and engineering disciplines. Both disciplines carry out investigations to understand the causal relationships between variables [11–13]. In addition, the novice practitioners in both disciplines have challenges in experimentation and tend to engage in confounded experiments [11,14,15]. Kuhn et al. (2000) in their investigation present that 6th and 8th grade students find multivariable causality challenging as they changed multiple variables at once and attributed the outcomes to all variables. Similarly, Crismond and Adams (2012) in their *Informed Design Teaching and Learning Matrix* suggest that beginning designers usually run confounded tests by changing multiple variables at the same time.

Engineers and scientists conduct experiments for various reasons. (See Table 1). Engineers use testing to gather data to specify design criteria, determine the optimization level of the prototype, evaluate whether the prototype achieves all of the requirements [16,17]. The feedback and data obtained from design experimentations can also be used to troubleshoot and improve the design solution to best meet the design parameters [18] (Lewis, 2006; Moore et al., 2014; National Research Council, 2012). Carrying out investigation in science is done to test a hypothesis and understand how empirical data compare to hypothesized results [8,19–21].

Table 1. The uses of experiments in engineering design and scientific inquiry

Engineering design	Scientific inquiry	Commonalities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand “why” “how” and “what” simultaneously • Contrasts “predictions and possible explanations (hypotheses) of prototype behavior” [11] • Observations and data collected are used to specify design criteria [17], to determine the optimization level of the prototype [16], and to identify solution strengths and weaknesses in order to re-design [22] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand “why” • Understand how empirical data compare to hypothesized results [8] • Observations and data collected are used to test existing theories and explanations or to develop new ones [17] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand causal relationships [11,12] • Beginners of both fields do confounded experiments [11,14]

Given K-12 teachers as well as students are more familiar with science as compared to engineering, it is important to study any variations in their understanding of conducting tests in design.

3 DESIGN & PROCEDURE

3.1 Participants and Study Context

This study took place in three middle schools (ages 12-14) (N=746). One 8th grade class in an urban setting allocated two weeks to design three unique solutions (N=64 students). Another school with three teachers in a suburban setting used the same design task and timeline, with 367 7th grade students. The third school with 315 7th grade students in a suburban setting participated in a design project with an authentic client led collaboratively by mathematics and science teachers and spent four weeks of design time with labs targeting specific science concepts outside of their time in Energy3D. The diversity in school demographics and approach to design allowed variations in student conceptions and generalizability of results to diverse school settings.

3.2 Design Challenge

Students at all three schools designed single family homes that consumed as little energy over the course of a year as possible while being cost effective, and also being attractive/comfortable. Students used Energy3D, a CAD design environment with cost and energy performance simulation capabilities (See Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Example student design & energy analysis in Energy3D
(<http://energy.concord.org/energy3d/>)

3.3 Data Collection with Conceptions of Design Test (CDT)

The Conceptions of Design Test (CDT) was used to collect data (See Figure 2). The CDT is adapted from an instrument designed by [3] to understand practicing designers' design language. Later revisions of the tool focused on college designers' conceptions of design [4,23,24]. The underlying conceptual framework of this instrument that serve as evidence of construct validity is that an important part of becoming a designer is learning the language of design.

CONCEPTIONS OF DESIGN TEST			Instructions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyzing data • Balancing trade-offs (<i>considering strengths & weaknesses</i>) • Brainstorming • Building • Communicating • Conducting tests • Evaluating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gathering information • Generating alternatives • Identifying constraints (<i>identifying limitations</i>) • Iterating (<i>making updates</i>) • Making decisions • Modeling • Planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prototyping (<i>creating a test version</i>) • Reflecting • Setting goals • Sketching (<i>using paper, computer, etc.</i>) • Understanding the problem • Using creativity 	<p>Selection: Which 5 would you consider MOST / LEAST important in terms of producing a high quality design?</p> <p>Open-ended response: For one of the MOST/LEAST important terms selected, please explain why</p>

Fig. 2. *Conceptions of Design Test*

4 DATA ANALYSIS

A multi method research approach [25] was used employing both quantitative and qualitative analysis of data collected with the Conception of Design Test (CDT).

4.1 Quantitative analysis

A McNemar's test, which is appropriate for paired dichotomous categorical data, was performed to determine whether students' tendency to prioritize "conducting test" as an important design practice has changed from pre- to post-administration [26].

4.2 Qualitative analysis

The second phase of the multi-method approach started by identifying the students who selected "conducting tests" as one of the five most important design practices and explained why this practice was important. Thirty-one students in pre-test and 52 students in post-test explained why conducting tests is important in design. We performed a thematic analysis [27] to systematically categorize students responses. In this systematic characterization, two researchers read the data and iteratively developed themes.

5 FINDINGS

5.1 Quantitative results

The McNemar test showed statistically significant differences. Significantly more students found "conducting tests" to be a most important design practice from pre- (29%) to post-test (36%) ($\chi^2 = 29.051$, $p = 0.003$). In addition, significantly fewer students considered it to be an unimportant design practice in the post-test (9%), compared to pre-test (16%) ($\chi^2 = .573$, $p = 0.000$). Moreover, students discussed "conducting tests" more frequently in the post-test, as the number of students discussing the term as important increased from 31 to 52 students.

5.2 Qualitative results

The thematic analysis provided insights into students' conceptualization of "conducting tests". The analysis resulted in six different conceptualizations of conducting tests,

grouped under two overarching themes (See Table 2). Diagnose-fix iterative cycle refers to micro-iterations often associated with design refinement and optimization. Transformative iterative cycle refers to macro-iterations where the iteration has more profound impact on the problem, process, or the solution.

Table 2. Variations in students' conceptualization of "conducting tests"

Theme	Purpose	Example of students responses
Diagnose-Fix Iterative Cycle	Test to determine whether the prototype is working as planned	<i>"I believe that Conducting Tests is the most important because you have to know if the product you are making works." [pre-test]</i>
	Test to find mistakes and flaws	<i>"One of the important design activities would be conducting tests. This step would help you determine a flaw in your design, and would give you ideas on how to fix it." [pre-test]</i>
	Test to find what works and what doesn't work	<i>"Conducting tests is important because it shows you what is good and what you need to work on. When you are conducting tests you can identify the problems. You can also see what you should keep and it gives you new information." [post-test]</i>
Transformative Iterative Cycle	Test to gather information on specific design criteria	<i>"Conducting tests are vital in this activity because the challenge is to find the most efficient home energy and price wise. Conducting tests gives the information needed to make improvements or fix constraints." [post-test]</i>
	Test to compare alternatives	<i>"I think Conducting tests is most important because, if you don't try different things, you won't be able to find the best of the options you have." [post-test]</i>
	Test to make strategic design decision	<i>"Conducting tests are important because they allow you to know what the best strategy is so that when you make a decision and begin to build you will not fail and have to tear down the building. Also, by doing this, you will have the most adequate and the best building because you have the ability of seeing all of the possible outcomes before." [pre-test]</i>

6 CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE RESEARCH

In the United States, the Next Generation Science Standards [28] and the broader STEM movement globally urge for the integration of engineering concepts and practices along with science practices in K-12 education. Yet, we need a better understanding of how students perceive these practices. This study suggests that after taking part in a design project, students recognized "conducting tests" as an important practice in design. Our analyses show variations in students' conceptualizations of design, recognizing its micro and macro iterations. In K-12 education, the emphasis is often put on micro iterations. It is important that curriculum and teaching practices also reinforce transformative iterations that are associated with strategic decision-making in design. While conducting tests is a practice very important to design, future research

is necessary examining both students' conceptions of this practice as well as their abilities to engage in systematic experimentation .

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